

A robust risk assessment method for energy planning scenarios on smart islands under the demand uncertainty

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Abstract

Energy systems with a high share of variable renewable energy are more vulnerable to sudden changes in the system operation. This is especially emphasized on small systems such as energy systems on geographical islands. Because of these reasons, there is a need for quantifying the risk of energy scenarios of such systems. This paper presents a novel robust risk assessment method under demand uncertainty for energy planning scenarios for the islands. The method uses graph theory for the representation of power system topology. The Poisson distribution is used for calculating the probability of power system element failure. The robust modelling approach is applied by the introduction of auxiliary variables and compared to the deterministic model results. Four energy planning scenarios for Unije island are modelled and subjugated to several power system outages resulting in a risk vector calculated as the product of probability vector and damage matrix. The study also presents a zero-import risk energy planning scenario for Unije island that is achieved for a system of 0.5 MW photovoltaic plant and 3.55 MWh battery storage system.

Keywords

Power system risk assessment; Smart islands; Graph theory; Power system optimization; Energy planning; Robust optimization

1. Introduction

The increasing effort of the European Union (EU) for decarbonization of energy systems imposes new challenges for scientists and engineers [1]. Due to their variability, integration of renewable energy sources (RES) in the energy systems reduce the security of supply and impose a new risk to power system operation. Therefore, it is necessary to implement new technology such as the energy storage systems (ESS) and the demand response (DR) for risk reduction when the power system is subjected to sudden and strong changes. Lately, a new concept of geographical islands as living labs emerges as a beneficial way of testing the new technology on islands as emphasized in [2]. The idea behind this is that, if it is possible to integrate a high amount of variable RES on islands, it will be possible to transfer and scale up the same solutions to similar locations on the mainland.

Methods and tools for energy planning of the islands have been presented in many studies. Duić et al. [3] presented a RenewIslands method for energy planning of the islands with an emphasis on different sector integration. The method was applied to Croatian islands in [4] where the authors analysed the effect of the interconnection between the island and concluded that interconnection can reduce the critical excess electricity power up to 22% when the islands are interconnected. Another study conducted on Cape Verde [5] showed that overall yearly costs of the energy system operation can reduce by 19% in comparison to the business as usual scenario when there is a higher penetration of wind coupled with the desalination plant and the pumped hydro plant. However, the method does not consider the risk assessment of generated scenarios. By applying the presented risk assessment method, these studies could be improved and it would be possible to quantify the risk level of each scenario.

To increase the possibility for RES integration technologies such as batteries and the DR are introduced in the power systems. To determine how flexible or resilient a particular energy scenario is, it is necessary to quantify the risk level of each scenario. Lund et al. [6] emphasizes the importance of energy system flexibility for RES integration. The paper analysed demand and production strategies to increase flexibility. The latest review of flexibility sources was provided in [7] where authors emphasized the importance of energy storage and demand response. The authors in [8] emphasized the importance of the proper pricing mechanism on a battery and PV system and concluded that the arbitrage for the batteries should be enabled in order to maximize the profitability of the investment. One of the possible solutions for

increasing the flexibility of the energy system is to use an integrated approach to energy planning as described in [9]. This research included refrigeration, smart EV charging and reverse osmosis technology to achieve flexibility and the authors conclude that 78.1% of the electricity demand can be met with the RES production by this approach.

The authors in [10] proposed a renewable mix that could produce 324.9 MWh/year and cover the entire demand of the island Ustica, however, the authors do not model the power system elements nor do they examine the failure probability. Similarly, the study [11] presented the approach for the energy transition from the diesel-based to the hybridized systems with a RES share of 50.4% for four analyzed islands. It would be interesting to apply the presented risk assessment approach to assess the trade-off between the risk level and the share of RES in electricity production. The authors in [12] underlined the importance of proper energy policy in the creation of energy planning scenarios, however without the quantification or inclusion of the risk assessment in the study.

A significant amount of energy planning methods and scenarios were proposed in these studies [3-12], however, none of them provided a risk analysis. Because of this, it remained unclear to what risk level are local communities exposed to when a particular energy planning scenario would be utilized. Application of the risk assessment method as an extension to analysed studies would contribute to the understanding of the overall impact on energy security on the islands.

The decision support system is presented in [13], where the expected load loss was taken as a measure of risk, but only larger systems such as Taiwan are considered and the system did not consider the cost that a possible power outage would cause. The authors in [14] presented an algorithm for maximizing the predictability of the electrical power system and the Power Flow Predictability Index. The authors showed that an increase in the 34.5% predictability index is possible with the increased system cost of 1.28%, however, the authors did not include the possibility for the power system elements failure nor the predictability of failures. Risk management in wind energy was analyzed in [15] with the conclusion that the lowest risk for wind energy integration is in the areas where governments have a long-term and clear vision of electricity price policy.

A method for assessing the safety of the electrical power system is presented in [16] where external risks are considered as threats caused by inclement weather, while load loss was considered as a measure of risk. The numerical results of the study [17] show that it is possible to achieve a 13.8% higher microgrid profit when considering the risk of unsafe power system parameters such as electricity price and the production from the variable RES. The study did

not analyze the specific operating conditions of the power system operation that may be a result of element outage. The power system risk assessment method based on the historical data and the predicted stochastic element failure for three scenarios in the power system is presented in [18] where the probability of the load loss and the average load loss was taken as a measure of risk. Besides using different measures of risk, the study did not use the robust approach and did not consider the curtailment of RES production.

The study [19] assessed the impact of different smart grid technologies and concluded that, when the load flexibility level is equal to 25%, it is possible to achieve monthly savings of 11.3 €. However, the study did not provide the impact analysis of different technologies on the risk level. Impact on the financial and technical aspects of running the power system under conditions of financial risk based on the behaviour of other players in the market was given in [20] where it was shown that the greatest financial profit of 10498.98 currency units for the case is achieved when the production of the solar power plants and the wind farms is managed under a single aggregator. Two scenarios for the microgrids with RES and electricity storage under the influence of risk are given in [21] where the author specifically considered the rate of change in solar radiation and wind speed between the two time periods, further examining the system's resistance to sudden changes.

Operation of the virtual power plant consisted of wind power, solar power, battery and diesel power under the conditions of the financial risks affecting its daily profit were explored in [22]. The authors in [23] used Pinch analysis for defining the energy planning scenarios and the calculation of the loss of power supply probability where they presented that it is possible to achieve the loss of power supply probability of 2.57%. Another study [24] presented the stochastic risk-averse approach for the microgrid planning under uncertainty and concluded that the stochastic approach results with 10,732 \$/year in comparison with the deterministic model for the best-case scenario. Multi-objective stochastic risk optimization model was presented in [25] with conclusion that the proposed approach reduced the overall expenditure by 23%. However, these studies did not model the power system elements and did not consider the possibility for the elements outage (e.g. line or transformer).

Quantitative risk analysis of functional failure in the fracturing system of unconventional natural gas was provided in [26]. Multi-objective risk analysis for a reforming reactor system was presented in [27] with the conclusion that P-graph can be used for representation of the process flow diagrams of the power plants. The proposed studies did not analyse energy systems as a whole nor they provided the method for risk assessment reduction when smart technology as energy storage is introduced.

From analysed literature, it is possible to conclude that the development of different energy planning scenarios for small renewable island systems is becoming increasingly important and the authors offer various methods for defining them. However, a risk assessment approach of developed scenarios for small island systems based on the grid elements failure probability, as well as potential damage that would occur as a result of an outage, was not analysed. The novel method developed within this study offers the possibility for such risk analysis and provides important information in the energy planning process. Moreover, this study proposes a robust approach for the risk assessment under the demand uncertainty which enables the evaluation of an entire range of possible scenarios – from most optimistic ones to most pessimistic. As such, the proposed method is beneficial for many different stakeholders such as investors in renewable technology or local island governments where outages occur more often as a result of harsh weather conditions. The method highlights a new aspect of long term development of the islands that is often based on financial parameters while the risk assessment for the islanders is neglected.

The hypothesis of this study is that, by using the presented robust risk assessment method based on graph theory, it is possible to quantify the risk level of energy planning scenarios for islands under the demand uncertainty. Relevant contributions of this paper are:

- A novel robust risk assessment method under the demand uncertainty that underlines the resilience of energy planning scenarios and provides another parameter in decision making for the smart islands
- The risk assessment analysis of the renewable energy planning scenarios conducted for Unije island and can be applied to numerous similar islands
- Comparison of deterministic and robust approach for risk assessment
- The case for a zero-import risk energy planning scenario for Unije island enabled the operation of the power system without any curtailment and any load shedding even when the fault on the interconnection occurs.

After the introduction section with literature review, gap analysis and description of the novelty of the developed method, the second section presents the novel risk assessment method developed within this study. The analysed case study is presented in the third section, while the fourth section presents the results of the study. The final section presents the concluding remarks of the study.

2. Materials and methods

The proposed method enables a risk assessment of the energy planning scenarios for the smart islands. This makes it a suitable decision-making tool for deciding what energy planning scenario or smart solution should be implemented. The method can be divided into several steps as follows:

- Step 1: Generate desired energy planning scenarios of an island.
- Step 2: Construct power system topology and belonging graph G together with probabilities for the failure of power system elements
- Step 3: Create robust optimization models for energy planning scenarios and define inputs for the optimization model
- Step 4: Apply outages on elements of the power system (bring the system to different states) and solve optimization models for every state of every scenario and measure the results
- Step 5: Calculate the risk vector of every energy planning scenario and analyse the results

Figure 1. Risk assessment method scheme

2.1. Power system elements outage probability calculation

Let $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E}, A)$ be the undirected graph which represents electrical power network of a small island with set of $\mathcal{N} = \{n_1, \dots, n_n\}$ nodes, $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}$ edges or links and where A is a matrix of ratios of an event occurring. Undirected edges are denoted as $e_{ij} = (n_i, n_j)$, the cardinality of a set of undirected edges is denoted as $|\mathcal{E}|$ and the matrix A satisfies $[A]_{ij} \neq 0 \Leftrightarrow e_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}$ and $[A]_{ij} = 0 \Leftrightarrow e_{ij} \notin \mathcal{E}$ where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $e_{ii} \notin \mathcal{E}$. Matrix A represents a failure ratio of the elements of the power system. The elements of the matrix are defined as $[A]_{ij} = a_{ij}$ where a_{ij} is a ratio of the outage of the given element of the power system. The importance of the graph theory is clear as there is a necessity for a objective mathematical formulation for connecting the ratio of outage of each particular element in the power system with the connections of different elements (objects) in the power system. Thus, the matrix of ratios A is created based on the graph theory.

A power system is a system of small probabilities and large damages. Small probabilities are described with a Poisson distribution which answers the question of what is the probability that an event occurs and is defined with expression (1). Poisson distribution is often applied in the power system modelling as in [28] for the transmission system or [29] for the distribution system.

$$\vartheta_m(N, \Delta t) = \frac{(a_{ij} \cdot \Delta t)^N \cdot e^{-a_{ij} \cdot \Delta t}}{N!} \quad (1)$$

Where N is the number of times that an event occurs in the given time Δt at a rate of a (events/time) where i and j stand for a particular element of the power system and correspond to e_{ij} . Therefore, a vector of probabilities is defined as $\theta = [\vartheta_1, \dots, \vartheta_{|\mathcal{E}|}]$ where $\vartheta_m \in \langle 0, 1 \rangle$ for all $m = 1, 2, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|$ and represents probabilities for fault at a given element of the power system.

2.2. Deterministic model

Islands' power systems are observed as the microgrids during the set of periods Ω^T , where $|\Omega^T| = 96$. Considered microgrids generally consist of non-flexible and flexible demand, RES and the ESS. The microgrid is subjugated to the dynamic pricing which opens the chance for

the microgrid components to provide flexibility to the system and allows final customers participation in the market on the distribution level. The objective of microgrid optimization is to move the system towards the equilibrium point where social welfare is maximized. Therefore, the objective function of the system is to minimize its operation cost or maximize its profit. It is considered that the buying and selling of electricity take place in the day-ahead electricity market. In this chapter, a general optimization model is presented that can be adjusted for the specific case study. The objective function $F: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as convex and derivative at every point of its domain and is represented by the following expression (2):

$$\max F \triangleq \max[\sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \lambda_t (E_t^s - E_t^b) - C_t] \quad (2)$$

Where λ_t is electricity market price at a given period t , E_t^s and E_t^b are sold and purchased energy to and from the electricity market and C_t are microgrid costs at a given period t . Costs of the microgrid are defined as the cost of curtailed energy and the cost of loss of load. A microgrid is subjugated to power balance constraint given with equation (3) for $\forall t \in \Omega^T, \forall pv \in \Omega^{PV}, \forall d, c \in \Omega^{ESS}, \forall w \in \Omega^W, \forall g \in \Omega^G$.

$$p_{g,t} + p_{w,t} + p_{pv,t} + p_{d,t} + p_{imp,t} + DR_t + LS_t = L_t + FL_t + p_{exp,t} + p_{c,t} \quad (3)$$

The left side of the equation presents power inputs to the microgrid and the right side presents power withdrawal elements. The power injections are PV generation ($p_{pv,t}$), wind power plant generation ($p_{w,t}$), conventional generator production ($p_{g,t}$), imported power ($p_{imp,t}$) to the microgrid, discharge from the ESS ($p_{d,t}$), load shedding (LS_t) as well as DR (DR_t) which reduces the need for electricity. The inflexible (L_t) and flexible load (FL_t), exported power ($p_{exp,t}$) and energy storage charging ($p_{c,t}$) represent the withdrawal of the electricity. Imported and exported electricity represent sold and purchased electricity on the day-ahead electricity market.

The total cost of the microgrid is expressed with equation (4) for $\forall t \in \Omega^T, \forall pv \in \Omega^{PV}, \forall w \in \Omega^W, \forall g \in \Omega^G$. $p_{pv,t}^{curt}$ is curtailed solar power from the set of PV plants Ω^{PV} . VPVC is the penalty for the curtailment of the PV production that represents the compensation for the loss of profit of the producer. Value of lost load (VOLL) is the cost of not delivering the electricity

to the customer. It is the estimated value and represents the amount that is a customer willing to pay for avoiding loss of supply.

Thermal generator model in the unit commitment is based on the models presented in [30]. There are several decisions that need to be made regarding the thermal generators in the day-ahead planning. These decisions are represented with the binary variables and include a start-up decision ($x_{g,t}$) and a shut-down decision ($z_{g,t}$) that are related to the start-up and shut-down costs (SU_g and SD_g) as in (4). The cost function (4) also includes a fuel cost function $F_g(p_{g,t})$ for the periods when generator is operating. The fuel cost function is usually in the quadratic form and should be linearized according to the procedure described in [30]. The thermal generator minimum and maximum output should also be constrained (5) and (6) with minimum (P_g^{min}) and maximum values (P_g^{max}). These constraints should be active only when the generator is operating, which is controlled with the binary variable $u_{g,t}$. The binary variable $u_{g,t}$ is equal to 1 if the generator is operating, otherwise it is equal to 0. Ramping up (RU_g) and down (RD_g) capabilities between the two consecutive periods are defined with equation (7).

The thermal generators usually cannot be started immediately nor can they be shut-down immediately. Thus, it is necessary to define minimum start-up (UT_g) and shut-down time (DT_g) of the generator. Equations (8) and (9) enable that the generators cannot be shut down until the shortest on time (UT_g) has passed and cannot be started-up before minimum down time (DT_g). Equation (10) defines the start-up action and equation (11) defines the shut down action. Moreover, equation (12) prevents simultaneous start-up and shut down of the generator.

The PV plant model is represented with equation (14) and the wind plant model with equation (15). The renewable units are designed in a way that the sum of produced energy and curtailed energy has to be equal to the maximum possible production $\Lambda_{pv,t}$ and $\Lambda_{w,t}$. The ESS model is given with equations (16) – (19) where $\mu_t \in \{0, 1\}$, $\xi \in [0,1]$. The SOC represents the state of charge of the storage, η_c and η_d the efficiency of charge and discharge and μ_t is the binary variable preventing simultaneous charging and discharging of the storage. ξ represents the share of total battery capacity that can be charged or discharged at a given time. The flexible load can provide significant flexibility to the island power system by providing the DR to the system. The most common way of providing flexibility to the power system on the islands is by desalination plants. Other ways for providing the DR is by heating storage, electric vehicles, automatic switching on and off of different house devices etc. A simplified DR model is given

with equation (20) and (21) where $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$. α_t and β_t represent the percentages of available flexible load for providing up and down DR services. ω represents the total amount of available DR for the observed period. Import and export power is limited by the capacity of the power line or physical constraints imposed by the power grid. Such constraints are mostly caused because of voltage issues, transient stability issues or other power quality issues. Islands systems are usually at the end of radially connected distribution grid which means that the voltage issues are more expressed in these areas. Thus, to preserve the stable conditions in the observed grid as well as in the surrounding grid, maximum and minimum export and import power constraints are modelled with equations (22) and (23).

$$C_t = \left(\sum_{g \in \Omega^G} (SU_g \cdot x_{g,t} + SD_g \cdot z_{g,t}) + \sum_{g \in \Omega^G} F_g(p_{g,t}) + VWC \cdot \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} P_{w,t}^{curt} + VPVC \cdot \sum_{pv \in \Omega^{PV}} P_{pv,t}^{curt} + VoLL \cdot LS_t \right) \cdot \Delta t, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (4)$$

$$P_g^{min} \cdot u_{g,t} \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_g^{max} \cdot u_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (5)$$

$$p_{g,t} \geq 0, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (6)$$

$$-RD_g \leq p_{g,t} - p_{g,t-1} \leq RU_g, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (7)$$

$$u_{g,t} - u_{g,t-1} \leq u_{g,k}, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T, k = t, \dots, \min\{t + UT_g - 1, |\Omega^T|\} \quad (8)$$

$$u_{g,t-1} - u_{g,t} \leq 1 - u_{g,k}, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T, k = t, \dots, \min\{t + DT_g - 1, |\Omega^T|\} \quad (9)$$

$$x_{g,t} \geq u_{g,t} - u_{g,t-1}, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (10)$$

$$z_{g,t} \geq u_{g,t-1} - u_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (11)$$

$$x_{g,t} + z_{g,t} \leq 1, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (12)$$

$$x_{g,t}, z_{g,t}, u_{g,t} \in \{0,1\}, \quad \forall g \in \Omega^G, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (13)$$

$$p_{pv,t} + p_{pv,t}^{curt} = \Lambda_{pv,t}, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (14)$$

$$p_{w,t} + p_{w,t}^{curt} = \Lambda_{w,t}, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (15)$$

$$SOC_t = SOC_{t-1} + (p_{c,t} \cdot \eta_c - \frac{p_{d,t}}{\eta_d}) \cdot \Delta t, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (16)$$

$$SOC^{min} \leq SOC_t \leq SOC^{max}, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (17)$$

$$p_{c,t} \cdot \Delta t \leq \xi \cdot SOC^{max} \cdot \mu_t, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (18)$$

$$p_{d,t} \cdot \Delta t \leq \xi \cdot SOC^{max} \cdot (1 - \mu_t), \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (19)$$

$$-\alpha_t \cdot FL_t \leq DR_t \leq \beta_t \cdot FL_t, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (20)$$

$$DR_t \cdot \Delta t \leq \omega, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (21)$$

$$P_{imp}^{min} \leq p_{imp,t} \leq P_{imp}^{max}, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (22)$$

$$P_{eks}^{min} \leq p_{exp,t} \leq P_{eks}^{max}, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (23)$$

2.3. Robust model formulation

Loss of load is the variable that has the highest effect on the damage caused by the power system outage. However, this is the uncertain variable that depends on the current demand of the observed system. Thus, equations (2)-(23) are valid only if demand L_t is considered as a deterministic parameter. Several techniques are available for modelling demand as an uncertain parameter. For stochastic scenario modelling [31], a probability density function of the observed parameter should be known. The membership function of the observed parameter should be known when fuzzy modelling is applied [32]. Stochastic scenario and fuzzy modelling are often computationally demanding. In this paper, a robust modelling approach [33] is applied. The robust modelling approach considers the uncertainty set to take the uncertainty parameter into the consideration. The uncertainty set is defined with the upper and lower values over the period that is available from the historic data. The boundaries are set to a 5th and 95th percentile. This approach assures that 95% of scenarios are under the upper boundary, while 5% of scenarios is under the lower boundary. The demand uncertainty interval is defined with expression (24):

$$\tilde{L}_t \in U(\tilde{L}_t) = \{\tilde{L}_t : L_t^{min} \leq \tilde{L}_t \leq L_t^{max}\}, \forall t \in \Omega^T \quad (24)$$

It is assumed that the only known values are minimum and maximum bounds of demand interval (L_t^{min} and L_t^{max}). The robust formulation of proposed MILP optimization problem was achieved by modifying the balance equation according to the [34] and [35].

Equality (3) should be transformed into two inequations as explained in [36]. Then, the robust counterpart of equation (3) of the deterministic problem can be written as (25) and (26):

$$\begin{aligned} & p_{g,t} + p_{w,t} + p_{pv,t} + p_{d,t} + p_{imp,t} + DR_t + LS_t \\ & \geq L_t + \phi_{L,t} \cdot \Gamma + \psi_{L,t} + FL_t + p_{exp,t} + p_{c,t}, \quad \forall t \in \Omega^T \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& p_{g,t} + p_{w,t} + p_{pv,t} + p_{d,t} + p_{imp,t} + DR_t + LS_t \\
& \leq L_t + \phi_{L,t} \cdot \Gamma + \psi_{L,t} + FL_t + p_{exp,t} + p_{c,t}, \forall t \in \Omega^T
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

In order to control the uncertainty interval, a conservativeness factor Γ is introduced. The conservativeness factor can range from 0 to 1 ($\Gamma \in [0,1]$) because there is only one uncertain value observed. The most optimistic result occurs for $\Gamma = 0$, when no deviation is considered. Increase of Γ_L parameter results with more pessimistic cases. The corresponding positive auxiliary variables are $\phi_{L,t}$, and $\psi_{L,t}$, necessary for the robust formulation modelling. Additional constraints (27) and (28) are necessary in order to take into account the uncertainty range.

$$\phi_{L,t} + \psi_{L,t} \geq \delta_{L,t}, \forall t \in \Omega^T \tag{27}$$

$$\phi_{L,t} \geq 0, \psi_{L,t} \geq 0, \forall t \in \Omega^T \tag{28}$$

The summation of auxiliary variables $\phi_{L,t}$ and $\psi_{L,t}$ needs to be greater or equal to the uncertainty range deviation $\delta_{L,t}$. The values of $\phi_{L,t}$ and $\psi_{L,t}$ are determined with the conservativeness factor Γ so that the worst case of uncertainty occurs. The final robust problem is defined with equations (2), (4)-(33) and (25)-(28).

2.4. Risk calculation

Let $S = \{S_1, \dots, S_Y\}$ represent set of energy planning scenarios, $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_{|\mathcal{E}|}\}$ set of modelled electric power system faults and $\mathcal{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times Y}$ damage matrix where $[\mathcal{D}]_{ij}$ is damage for every i energy planning scenario subjugated to fault j . Elements of the damage matrix are calculated with presented optimization models. Risk vector $\mathcal{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times Y}$ is defined as the product of probability vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times |\mathcal{E}|}$ and damage matrix \mathcal{D} and is defined as follows with equation (29):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vartheta_1 \\ \vartheta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vartheta_m \end{bmatrix}^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{D}_{11} & \dots & \mathcal{D}_{1Y} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathcal{D}_{|\mathcal{E}|1} & \dots & \mathcal{D}_{|\mathcal{E}|Y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{R}_1 \\ \mathcal{R}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{R}_Y \end{bmatrix}^T \tag{29}$$

3. Case study

Case study for testing presented method is conducted on small island Unije located in Kvarner archipelago in Croatia. Unije island has 16,77 km² of area and 88 inhabitants during winter.

During summer the number of people on the island reaches up to six times more residents than during winter. Unije has a 400 kVA substation that is connected with a 10 kV cable to the nearest island Vele Srkane. All the power for these and other small islands is provided from 4 MVA substation on the island of Lošinj. The power system of Unije is dependent on the availability of 10 kV cables from Unije to Lošinj because it is the only way of importing power to the island. There have been two faults on these cables in the period 2011 – 2018 [37] that caused power loss for residents of Unije island. Because of this, Unije represents an excellent location as a living lab for risk evaluation that can later be transferred to similar locations on the mainland. In order to choose the right energy planning scenario for microgrid, there is a need for risk assessment on each scenario. Therefore, this paper observes several different energy planning scenarios and evaluates risk by implementing the described method for each scenario.

3.1. Observed scenarios

Scenarios are presented in Table 1:

Table 1. Analysed scenarios for Unije island

Scenario	PV [MW]	ESS [MWh]	DR
S_0	0	0	No
S_1	1	0	Yes
S_2	0	1	Yes
S_3	1	0.5	Yes
“Zero-import risk”	TBD	TBD	Yes

It is assumed that the DR is provided by the desalination plant on the island represented with the flexible demand of 25 kW. The desalination plant is capable of providing the DR in the amount of 70% of its occupancy at a given period with a total amount of DR being less or equal to 200 kWh. The flexible load is not taken into account in the business as usual scenario (S_0), because the desalination plant is currently not used for providing the DR.

3.2. Network topology

Network topology of the island Unije is given in Figure 2 where existing elements are presented with the black line and elements that need to be built for implementation of energy planning scenarios are presented with the blue line. Presented elements that will be integrated include the PV plant, PV substation, flexible load and energy storage system. The existing elements are a 10 kV connection to the mainland, a transformer with a ratio of 10/0.4 kV and island load.

Figure 2. Unije power system with the existing elements marked with the black colour and elements that will be integrated marked with the blue colour

With defined topology and graph representation of topology, it is possible to calculate matrix A . The elements of matrix A are based on the historic data and represent the rate of fault occurrence at a given element of the system. Vector θ consists of the long term failure probabilities of particular elements of the power system network. In the case of Unije, calculated probabilities are the probability of failure of any line from feeder to Unije, which is represented only as one aggregated line in Figure 2, probability of failure of the transformer that connects the loads and the battery with the power line and combined probability of the failure of the line and the transformer that connects the PV plant to the power system. These probabilities correspond with edges e_{12} , e_{23} , e_{24} that connect belonging nodes in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Graph representation of Unije power system

From data available at [37], it is possible to conclude that the failure rate for cables connecting feeder Lošinj and Unije is 0.286 failure per year. The transformer failure happens at a rate of 0.02 failure per year [38] which is significantly rarer than line faults. This is expected because of the high reliability and protection of transformers while cables and lines are vulnerable to outside effects such as weather changes. Cable and transformer that connect PV plant with the power system have to be built and their rate of occurrence can be calculated from the data available from [39] and [40] as the sum of the probabilities of failure of cable or transformer and amounts to 0.041 failures per year. The connection cable of PV and the power grid is significantly shorter (300 m) than cables connecting Unije to the feeder which means a significantly lower probability of failure. Therefore it is possible to construct matrix A for the described power system as:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.286 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.286 & 0 & 0.02 & 0.041 \\ 0 & 0.02 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.041 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The simulation is considered for two days in august with the highest demand. This period is characterized by the highest demand, thus it is most relevant for the risk calculation. In order to enable the possibility to compare results one to another, the simulation considers that all faults occurred at 10 am and lasted until the end of the simulation.

3.3. Input data and optimization models

Input data for the optimization models is calculated and obtained from known analysis and the available data. The data is represented on a half an hour basis. The data for solar power production is obtained from the Optimal grid connection study [40] conducted for Unije island. The historical demand data is available from the study [41] and presented in Figure 4. The upper and lower boundaries are set in such a way that a two-sigma probability is assured. The data for electric energy prices were obtained from the historical data [42]. The simulation considers the case where values for the demand, solar production and prices occur for two consecutive days.

Figure 4. Electric energy demand for a peak summer day

The penalties for the wind and PV curtailment are calculated according to data available at [43] while the value of the lost load is calculated on the national level as the ratio between the gross domestic product and the annual electric energy consumption. The remaining data is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameter values for the optimization problem

Parameter	Value	Unit
VPVC/VWC	105.58	€/MWh
VOLL	2840	€/MWh
η_c	0.95	-
η_d	0.9	-
ξ	0.5	-
α	0	-
β	0.7	-
ϑ	0.2	MWh
$p_{imp}^{min}, p_{exp}^{min}$	0	MW
$p_{imp}^{max}, p_{exp}^{max}$	2.0	MW
Δt	0.5	h

Scenario S_0

Scenario S_0 represents the business as usual scenario. This means that island has no newly installed technology and there is no DR available. The objective function of the optimization model for such a scenario is defined with equation (30):

$$\max F^{S_0} \triangleq \max[\sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \lambda_t(-E_t^b) - VoLL \cdot LS_t \cdot \Delta t] \quad (30)$$

Subjected to equations (3), (22) and (23) for the deterministic case and with equations (22), (23), (25)-(28) for the robust model.

Scenario S_1

Scenario with a solar power plant of 1 MW is described by Scenario S_1 . The island is not dependent on power import when the PV plant production is high enough to cover the demand. At the same time, the excess power production is sold on the day-ahead electric energy market and the microgrid is generating profit. At this point, the DR is available from the desalination plant. Scenario S_1 is described with the following objective function (31):

$$\max F^{S_1} \triangleq \max[\sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \lambda_t(E_t^s - E_t^b) - VPVC \cdot P_{pv,t}^{curt} \cdot \Delta t - VoLL \cdot LS_t \cdot \Delta t] \quad (31)$$

Subjected to equations (3), (14), (20)-(23) for the deterministic model and to constraints (14), (20)-(23) and (25)-(28) for the robust optimization model.

Scenario S_2

The conditions in the islands' microgrid with the battery storage of 1 MW are described with scenario S_2 . The battery allows microgrid to arbitrage on the electric energy market by buying the electricity during periods of low price and selling it during periods of high price, thus providing the support for the external electric power system. The optimization model for scenario S_2 is given with equation (32):

$$\max F^{S_2} \triangleq \max[\sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \lambda_t(E_t^s - E_t^b) - VoLL \cdot LS_t \cdot \Delta t] \quad (32)$$

Subjected to equations (3), (16)-(23) for the deterministic case and to equations (16)-(23) and (25)-(28) for the robust case.

Scenario S_3

Final scenario S_3 represents the combination of 1 MW PV plant and 0.5 MW battery. The optimization model balances the microgrid so that its profit is maximized. The objective function of scenario S_3 is given with equation (33):

$$\max F^{S_3} \triangleq \max \left[\sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \lambda_t (E_t^S - E_t^b) - VPVC \cdot P_{pv,t}^{curt} \cdot \Delta t - VoLL \cdot LS_t \cdot \Delta t \right] \quad (33)$$

and is subjected to the constraints given with equations (3), (14), (16)-(23) for the deterministic model and with equations (14), (16)-(13) and (25)-(28) for the robust model.

“Zero-import risk” scenario

Additionally, this paper uses the described method for investigating the possibility for Unije island to become energy self – sufficient. For this purpose, special attention will be given to the scenario S_3 in order to investigate the required amount of installed PV plant power as well as the battery capacity for achieving a zero-import risk level. The scenario is simulated for the case when the fault occurs on Unije connection to the mainland at 10 am and lasts until the end of the simulation.

4. Results

The key outcome of the proposed method is the risk level that is used as a comparison indicator between the different energy planning scenarios. The risk level defined as in this paper may be considered as a reasonable amount of investment that should be made in order to prevent the potential outage of elements. However, the purpose of this method and the risk value as a result of it is to enable comparison between different scenarios. If one would want to calculate the risk value of already existing scenario in order to calculate the necessary periodical investment in order to prevent outages, it would be necessary to modify the proposed method so that it considers wider range of possible outages and their likelihood of occurrence.

4.1. Deterministic results

The risk should be calculated for the worst case which is during maximum demand on the island. Such demand can happen at any time during two summer months July and August, thus it is needed to calculate the probabilities of failure for that period. The probability vector θ is given with (34):

$$\theta = [0.046 \quad 0.0034 \quad 0.0069] \quad (34)$$

The results of optimization problems or caused damage for every scenario subjugated to a series of described faults is presented with damage matrix \mathcal{D} (35):

$$\mathcal{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 15,751.2 & 8,606.7 & 13,308.8 & 6,350.7 \\ 15,751.2 & 15,467.2 & 13,308.8 & 14,388 \\ 0 & 1,683.9 & 0 & 1,683.9 \end{bmatrix} \text{ €} \quad (35)$$

Rows of the matrix represent the energy scenario S_i and columns present fault v_i . For example, when a fault happens on interconnection (v_1) for the energy planning scenario S_2 the damage equals 13,308.8 €. With defined probability vector θ and the damage matrix \mathcal{D} it is possible to calculate the risk vector \mathcal{R} by using expression (29). The results are also visually presented in Figure 5.

$$\mathcal{R} = \begin{bmatrix} 778.1 \\ 460.1 \\ 657.5 \\ 352.7 \end{bmatrix}^T \text{ €} \quad (36)$$

Figure 5. The quantified risk for analysed scenarios

The results indicate that the lowest risk is present in the energy planning scenario S_3 which represents the combination of a 1 MW PV plant and 0.5 MWh battery. Such results were expected because the implementation of different technologies enables easier operation of the system with lower cost in general. Table 3 presents the total cost of the system for two analysed days for different scenarios with applied faults as well as the cost in the normal operation of the system (v_0).

Table 3. Total operation cost in euros [€] for a given scenario and occurred fault for the deterministic model

Scenario	v_0	v_1	v_2	v_3
S_0	-378.9	-15,812	-14,743.4	-378.9
S_1	798	-8,433.6	-14,357.3	-1,822.7
S_2	-354.3	-13,406.9	-13,406.9	-354.3
S_3	807.2	-6,173.7	-13,296.7	-1,813.4

The total cost of the system shows that the system is making a profit only for S_1 and S_3 scenarios which are scenarios with the PV power plant. Other values are in correlation with the calculated energy planning scenario risks.

4.2. Robust model results

The operation cost of all scenarios under the different budget of uncertainties is summarized in Table 4. The results indicate that the operation cost increases (or the profit reduces) as the conservativeness coefficient increases. Scenario S_3 had the lowest operation cost (or the highest profit) for all faults in the system.

Table 4. The operation cost in euros [€] of all scenarios for a different budget of uncertainty levels

$\Gamma = 0$				
Scenario/Fault	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4
S_0	-297.9	-12,434.9	-12,434.9	-297.9
S_1	879	-6,633.6	-10,980.2	-1,822.7
S_2	-273.3	-10,029.8	-10,029.8	-273.3

S_3	888.3	-4,374.1	-9,919.6	-1,813.4
$\Gamma = 0.5$				
Scenario/Fault	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4
S_0	-389.9	-16,274.2	-16,274.2	-389.9
S_1	787	-8,736.5	-14,819.5	-1,914.7
S_2	-365.3	-13,869.1	-13,869.1	-365.3
S_3	796.2	-6,477	-13,758.9	-1,905.5
$\Gamma = 1$				
Scenario/Fault	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4
S_0	-460	-19,189.2	-19,189.2	-460
S_1	716.9	-10,118	-17,734.4	-1,984.8
S_2	-435.4	-16,784	-16,784	-435.4
S_3	726.1	-7,858.5	-16,673.8	-1,957.6

Figure 6 presents the damage level for four scenarios for different Γ values and different faults v_i . The damage caused by the fault v_3 (loss of PV production) is the lowest for all scenarios. This result is expected as the penalty for the PV curtailment is significantly lower than the penalty for the loss of load. Additionally, scenarios S_0 and S_2 do not have the PV installed which means that there is no damage to these scenarios for the v_3 outage. This is reflected in the green bars in Figure 6. The influence of the PV plant is visible for the fault on the interconnection (v_1), where the presence of the PV plant reduces the damage significantly (Figure 6 (b) and (d)). This is an important result as the fault on interconnection (v_1) is 13 times more likely than the fault on the transformer (v_2). The implementation of the battery storage system leads to the overall damage reduction for faults v_1 and v_2 as can be observed in Figure 6 (c) and (d).

Figure 6. Damage for four scenarios (a), (b), (c) and (d) for different budgets of uncertainty Γ

The risk values for all scenarios for different levels of conservativeness are presented in Figure 7. It is possible to observe that, as the Γ parameter increases, the risk level increases as well. Figure 7 also shows a higher increase of risk level for the scenarios S_0 and S_2 than for the scenarios S_1 and S_3 as the uncertainty increases. The risk level increased for 332.5 € for S_0 and S_2 (when $\Gamma = 0 \rightarrow 1$), while, for S_1 and S_3 , it increases for 181.9 € (when $\Gamma = 0 \rightarrow 1$). This result confirms the importance of the PV plant for risk reduction as the scenarios with the PV had the lowest risk level. Moreover, the risk level for the scenarios with PV (S_1 and S_3) did not increase as rapidly as for scenarios S_0 and S_2 when the uncertainty budget increases, which is another confirmation of the positive PV influence on the risk level.

Figure 7. Risk values for all scenarios under different uncertainty budgets Γ

The battery storage influence is also visible in Figure 7. Scenario S_2 has a 120.7 € lower risk level than scenario S_0 , while scenario S_3 has 107.4 € lower risk than scenario S_1 . The consideration of the battery system for scenarios S_2 and S_3 resulted in lower risk in comparison to the scenarios without battery storage. However, the implementation of the battery system resulted in the same value of risk reduction for all uncertainty budget values, while the implementation of the PV plant resulted in higher risk reduction as the uncertainty budget increased.

Mean risk values together with the bar chart of the robust optimization model solutions is presented in Figure 8. The overall order of the scenarios remained the same with scenario S_3 as the lowest risk scenario and S_0 as the highest risk scenario. The obtained mean values were similar to the deterministic model values. The highest difference of risk value occurred for scenario S_2 and amounted to 22.75 € (3.5% increase) in comparison to the deterministic model solution. The results of the robust model confirmed the result of the deterministic model that scenario S_3 is the best-case scenario in terms of the risk assessment.

Figure 8. Mean values and quartiles for robust solutions of risk values

4.3. Zero – import risk scenario

The zero-import risk analysis investigated the impact of different PV plant power and battery capacity installations on the risk level under the different budget of uncertainty values when the fault on the interconnection occurs. As previously elaborated, this analysis is important for islands with a weak connection to the mainland such as Unije island. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. The risk assessment analysis of the S_3 scenario for the different PV, battery and budget of uncertainty values

The analysis was conducted for four cases considering installations of 0, 0.5, 1 and 1.5 MW PV plant, while battery capacity varies from 0 MWh to 4 MWh under three different Γ parameter values (0, 0.5 and 1). When comparing the scenarios with the different installations it is possible to observe that scenario with a 0 MW PV power plant needs a battery with a significantly higher capacity than 4 MWh for securing the supply in case of an outage. The best solution is achieved for the scenario with a 0.5 MW PV power plant and 3.55 MWh battery capacity. These values of installed PV power and battery capacity assure that the risk value is equal to zero and that Unije island is 100% renewable and energy self – sufficient. For this case, after the interconnection fault occurs, Unije successfully transits to the island regime with the secured supply of the island without any curtailed energy.

The scenarios with 1 and 1.5 MW PV power plant can also achieve 100% renewable self – sufficient Unije island but with a battery capacity significantly higher than 4 MWh. This is because the risk is the function of the unsupplied load as well as the curtailed energy. Because of the oversized PV power plant in these two scenarios, there is a need for the battery with much higher capacity than in the scenario with 0.5 MW in order to store all excess power from the PV power plant.

Another interesting analysis is when PV production curtailment is not penalized. Thus, Figure 10 presents the required battery capacity for supplying all the load when a fault on the interconnection occurs for the different PV power and the uncertainty budget values. For battery capacity values presented in Figure 10, there is no load shedding when the interconnection outage occurs and the entire load is supplied but with curtailed production from the PV plant. For the most pessimistic case ($\Gamma = 1$), a 0.2 MWh less battery capacity is needed when the PV power increases from 0.5 MW to 1 MW. However, further increase of the PV power results in

only 0.05 MWh less battery capacity. This result indicates that a further increase of installed PV power would not result in improvement in terms of the lower battery capacity required. This is because PV can only supply load during the day, while, for the other periods of the day, the battery capacity has to be high enough to supply the entire load. For more optimistic cases this relation is less expressed as the overall demand is lower.

Figure 10. Required battery capacity for the elimination of load shedding when interconnection outage occurs

5. Discussion

This study presented a novel risk assessment approach for energy planning scenarios on islands. The main finding of this study is that the lowest risk value was achieved for the scenarios with joint management of a 1 MW PV plant and 0.5 MWh battery storage. This result was obtained by modelling the outage probability of the power system elements as well as the damage that occurred as a result of the outage.

The study showed that it is possible to determine the capacities of the installed technologies so that they ensure the island operation in the case of interconnection outage. Figure 7 showed that the risk value can significantly differ from the most optimistic case ($\Gamma = 0$) to the most pessimistic case ($\Gamma = 1$). The most optimistic and pessimistic case were observed from the standpoint of the system, meaning that the most favourable case is for $\Gamma = 0$. This result is significant because it indicates that the islands with higher expected demand (e.g. more developed tourist or industry sector) should be more risk-aware.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the most relevant research of the risk assessment in energy planning was conducted in [44]. The study [44] used the Levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) as a relevant measure of risk. The Monte Carlo analysis was used for modelling of outage history of energy component and proved to be efficient for large systems (e.g. on a country level). This study was designed for smaller systems on the island level, thus it was possible to gather historical data about the outages. Moreover, the study presented in this paper used the risk assessment method for comparison of different energy planning scenarios, while the study [44] used it for different policy recommendations. The results of this study also underlined the findings in [45]. Both studies showed that an increase of RES share in the system resulted in lower risk. However, the method proposed in the study [45] is only applicable to the joint heating and electricity sector.

Many studies consider risk as a means to describe the uncertainty in the energy system operation. Different implementations of risk in the optimization model can be found; the stochastic approach was used in [46], conditional value at risk was considered in [47], a robust approach was implemented in [48] similarly as in this study. However, the studies that analyse the outage possibilities as a part of the energy planning process are rare although they can offer important information. This study utilizes a robust approach in modelling the uncertainty, however, in comparison with previous studies, this study placed the focus on the risk quantization of each energy planning scenario. This allows an island to define the risk level to which it would be exposed in case of an outage which enables additional information while planning renewable energy scenarios.

Another result of this study showed that it is possible to determine the necessary installed capacities of PV and battery storage in order to secure the supply in case of an interconnection outage. As the technology that enables island operation of the power system (e.g. grid forming inverters) is becoming increasingly available, this analysis is becoming more important. Small islands may secure their electricity supply by installing a higher amount of controllable technology (e.g. batteries). This may often be possible without the significant increase in cost and the risk assessment method proposed in this study enables identification of such situations.

There are several limitations to this study. The optimization algorithm presented in the study aims to maximize the social welfare of the observed system. This may not always be the case as different stakeholders with different objectives participate in the power system operation. However, the power system operation in case of an outage is defined with the grid code. Thus,

it would be reasonable that the operation of all stakeholder in the power system would be oriented towards the preservation of the secure operation in case of an outage.

The proposed method will be applied to multi-energy systems in future research. This will include transportation, water, heating and electricity systems. With the proposed method, it will be possible to quantify the risk reduction when different sectors are integrated and jointly operated in comparison to the conventional operation where all sectors operate independently.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented a novel robust method for risk assessment of the energy planning scenarios for islands under the demand uncertainty with a case study conducted on Unije island. The obtained results demonstrated that it is possible to quantify risk levels of analysed energy planning scenarios on the smart islands together with the following conclusions:

- The obtained results showed that the risks for the four analysed scenarios for the deterministic model were equal to 778.1, 460.1, 657.5 and 352.7 € indicating that it is possible to quantify risk and differentiate the energy planning scenarios based on the risk level.
- The energy planning scenario with the lowest risk is S_3 scenario with risk equal to 259.1 € for the most optimistic case ($\Gamma = 0$) and 441 € for the most pessimistic case ($\Gamma = 1$)
- The zero-import risk scenario for the island of Unije is achieved for 0.5 MW PV plant and 3.55 MWh of the battery storage which means that the island can operate without any curtailed energy when the interconnection is lost.
- A case study on Unije shows that it is possible to create completely renewable islands that are energy independent from the mainland
- The presented method provides additional information – risk level of each energy planning scenario – to the experts, investors and decision-makers that are not available in the current studies

Future research will be oriented towards the exploration of additional possibilities for the risk quantification of the energy planning scenarios on the smart islands as well as the other options for uncertainty management.

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Appendix A

Case study – Tilos island

In order to illustrate the possible applications of the method, additional example is provided in this Appendix A. In this example, a case of Greek island Tilos is considered. The two main consumption centers on Tilos are Megalo Chorio Village and Livadia Village (represented with L1 and L2 on Figure A1). The Tilos island has a electrical interconnection to the Kos island that can supply the Tilos island with the electric energy with the existing thermal unit. There are several installations on the Tilos island that include a 1.45 MW backup diesel generator, a 0.8 MW wind power plant, a 0.8MW/2.88 MWh battery storage facility and a 0.16 MW PV plant.

In this case study, the effect of installation of these technologies with respect to the risk will be observed according to the scenarios presented in Table A1. Important note regarding the diesel generator is that it is run manually, thus it was assumed that at least 2 hours are necessary to start it up on the grid. The data for the case study can be found in [49] and [50], while the other data relevant for the calculation is provided in Table A2. It is also assumed that the outage happens at 10am of the first day and that the observed period are the two highest demand days. The Tilos power grid topology and the corresponding graph is provided in the Figure A1. Different scenarios are marked in different colors for better visualization.

Results and discussion

The results of the Tilos case study are given with the vector \mathcal{R} and in Figure A2. It can be seen that the scenario with the highest risk is the initial scenario when there is only interconnection available as a power supply. Installation of diesel generator significantly reduces the risk of loss of power supply. However, there is still risk because the generator is operated manually, which means that some load will be lost until the time the diesel generator starts up. The detailed mathematical model presented in the Materials and methods section enables to account for such feature. Installation of 0.8 MW wind power plant and the battery storage system 0.8MW/2.88 MWh reduced the risk in comparison to the original scenario, however the risk is higher than for S_{A2} scenario because there was not enough wind capacity installed. The final, S_{A4} , scenario that included the 0.16 MW solar power plant in addition to the wind power and battery storage system achieved the lowest risk.

There are several reasons why this is the case. First, the battery storage system has a high enough capacity to successfully integrate variable renewables in the system and use the energy produced from these units when necessary. Secondly, in comparison to the diesel generator, the renewable energy units are dispersed across the topology of the grid. This is another benefit of including the graph theory in the method proposed in this paper. Finally, with grid forming inverters, the units connected with the energy electronics on the grid can be run automatically, while backup diesel generators do not have this possibility, thus causing loss of load until the time they are started.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.257 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.257 & 0 & 0.02 & 0.02 & 0.037 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.02 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.02 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.037 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.02 & 0.01 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.02 & 0 & 0.02 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 & 0.02 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathcal{R} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0416 \\ 0.0034 \\ 0.0034 \\ 0.0063 \\ 0.0034 \\ 0.0017 \\ 0.0034 \end{bmatrix}^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 60700.74 & 3626.68 & 5276.36 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 944.8 & 944.8 \\ 23794.94 & 1326.28 & 23794.94 & 23794.94 \\ 36905.98 & 36905.98 & 36905.8 & 30396.52 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 716.25 \\ 36905.98 & 36905.98 & 36905.98 & 36905.98 \\ 36905.98 & 36905.98 & 36905.98 & 36905.98 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 3026.78 \\ 576.11 \\ 724.34 \\ 466.27 \end{bmatrix}^T \text{ €}$$

Figure A2. Results of the Tilos case study – highest risk for the scenario without any interventions; lowest risk for the scenario with battery storage system, wind and solar generation

It can be concluded that the proposed method can be universally applied to many different case studies on geographical islands. The results of the method provide a unique and original insight in the risk levels of energy planning scenarios, thus presenting a useful tool for the energy planners, policy makers and local communities.

Nomenclature

Indices and sets		\tilde{L}_t	Uncertain load at period t [MW]
i, j	Scenario and fault indexes	$P_{imp/exp}^{min/max}$	Minimum and maximum import and export power [MW]
t, k	Time periods	FL_t	Flexible load at time t [MW]
\mathcal{N}	Set of nodes	$\delta_{L,j}$	Deviation of actual load to forecasted load [MW]
\mathcal{E}	Set of lines	Variables and matrixes	
S	Set of scenarios	x	General variable
V	Set of outages	E_t^S, E_t^B	Sold and bought energy on day-ahead market [MWh]

\mathbb{R}	Set of real numbers	C_t	Cost of microgrid operation [€/MWh]
e_{ij}	Undirected edges	$P_{d,t}, P_{c,t}$	Discharging and charging battery power at time t [MW]
$\Omega^{\mathcal{T}}$	Set of time periods	$P_{imp,t}, P_{exp,t}$	Import and export power of observed grid [MW]
Ω^{ESS}	Set of energy storage systems	SOC_t	State of charge of the battery [MWh]
Ω^{PV}	Set of solar power plants	P_t^d, P_t^c	Discharging and charging power of the battery [MW]
Ω^G	Set of conventional generators	$p_{g,t}$	Production from the conventional generator [MW]
Ω^W	Set of wind power plants	$p_{w,t}$	Production from the wind power plant [MW]
Parameters		$P_{pv,t}$	Solar power plant production at time t [MW]
SU_g, SD_g	Start-up and shut down cost of the generator [€/MWh]	$P_{w,t}^{curt}$	Curtailed power from wind power plant at time t [MW]
RU_g, RD_g	Ramp-up and ramp down of the generator [MW]	$F_g(\cdot)$	Quadratic cost function of generator [€/MWh]
UT_g, DT_g	Minimum up and down time of the generator [h]	$x_{g,t}, z_{g,t}, u_{g,t}$	Binary variables for generator operation control
ξ	Factor for limiting battery charge and discharge	$P_{pv,t}^{curt}$	Curtailed power from solar power plant at time t [MW]
$SOC^{min/max}$	Minimum and maximum battery state of charge [MWh]	μ_t	Binary variable for energy storage system

η_c	Charging efficiency	DR_t	Demand response at time t [MW]
η_d	Discharging efficiency	$\phi_L, \psi_{L,t}$	Auxiliary variables
$\Lambda_{i,t}^{PV}$	Maximum available solar power plant generation [MW]	θ	Probability vector
VPVC, VWC	Value of curtailed solar and wind power generation [€/MWh]	\mathcal{D}	Damage matrix
VOLL	Value of lost load [€/MWh]	\mathcal{R}	Risk matrix
λ_t	Electric energy price at period t [€/MWh]	Abbreviations	
α	Factor for downward demand response limitation	EU	European Union
β	Factor for upward demand response limitation	DR	Demand response
Γ	Budget of uncertainty	RES	Renewable energy sources
ϑ	Probability of an event occurring	ESS	Energy storage system
a	Ratio of an event occurring	PHP	Pumped hydro storage
N	Number of times an event occurred	PV	Solar power plant
L_t^{min}, L_t^{max}	Minimum and maximum load at period t [MW]	CVaR	Conditional value at risk

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